

Study on Opinions of Younger Generation on Features of Non-Indian Brands Using NLTK, Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis, Supervised Learning and Hybrid Ensemble Learning in the Context of "Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan"

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ABSTRACT

After the honorable prime minister's announcement on be vocal for local, some Indian Brands started growing in Indian market. Also, many new startups have begun after the announcement the Special economic and comprehensive package of INR 20 lakh crores to fight COVID-19 pandemic in India to revive the Indian economy, to help farmers, migrant workers, and to revive the industrial sector, under the mission 'Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan' or the Self-reliant India campaign. The Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis finds the aspects or features from a sentence first and then the sentiment score of that aspect. The aspect is usually a feature or a noun. The sentiment score can be either positive or negative or zero. We further applied the supervised machine learning (ML) algorithms – support vector machine (SVC), Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB), Random Forest (RF) and K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), to check the sentiment analysis algorithms accuracy. On average the ML algorithms give 0.9647 accuracy whereas the hybrid ensemble model gives the accuracy 0.9690 with TextBlob and the SpacyTextBlob algorithms. The VADER sentiment analysis gives little better accuracy. As per it, the average accuracy of all four ML algorithms is 0.9791 whereas with hybrid ensemble model, it is 0.9820. For this study, we have collected from the website <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/nicapotato/womens-ecommerce-clothing-reviews>. The training and test ratio used is 70:30.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Brands can be helpful in strengthening a person's identity. Hence, consumers use brands as instruments for reflecting their personality and individual goals. The self-concept as a vital component of emotional aspects, boosts attitudinal loyalty towards a brand. (K. P., Zeynep,

G. C., 2007) Vocal for Local is not just about buying the Indian brands only being an Indian as far as possible but also to bring the brand up to that quality, which we can export to other countries. To promote the idea to be Vocal for local, we should first understand about what is that factors or features, which make non-Indian brands so popular, even being it extremely costly sometimes and even the money we spend will be shared with non-Indians.

The “Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan” has been praised for reintroducing the idea of Swaraj as a redemptive tool for the post-pandemic Indian economy. If implemented effectively, it can help achieve the dream of India being economically stable, technologically superior, self-reliant in its needs. Buying products from small vendors, even if with little more price helps their families to run their life smoothly and they eventually can help government by paying more tax and thus it makes Indian economy stronger. By buying from local vendor, our money will remain in our country only and because of that our Indian economy may become more stronger, as rightly said by our prime minister – Vocal for Local.

We have studied for the features of non-Indian products using aspect-based sentiment analysis, which make them superior over Indian products. We have collected the data from the website <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/nicapotato/womens-ecommerce-clothing-reviews>. We performed aspect-based analysis on amazon data to find the attributes and their description. We then calculated the sentiment from each description using VADER sentiment analysis. As it is too difficult to include every description into consideration for counting each description’s frequency, we have just taken top 30 description, whose sentiment is > 0.5 .

Research Objective To clarify why some non-Indian products are more popular among young generations.

II .LITERATURE REVIEW

This study was conducted to analyze consumer preference for global brands of various products. The Modi Ji Prime Minister of India has initiated the important mission for Indians known as "Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan" (ABA) to be self-reliant and be vocal for local for resilient India.

The "Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan" is an important mission for the economic revival and progress of the Indian economy during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The term refers to making India "a bigger and more important part of the global economy," as well as pursuing policies that are effective, sustainable, and resilient, as well as being self-sustaining and self-generating.

Though there are various challenges Faced by Local Enterprises, one of the major challenges is the Global Competition. World Bank. (2020): The globalized nature of markets exposes local enterprises to intense competition from international counterparts. Meeting international quality standards and overcoming trade barriers can be daunting for smaller businesses, requiring strategic support and policy interventions.

This study finds the features that attract the young generation to buy global brands. What are the characteristics of the global brands that makes the young generation of India to buy the global products. To study those features we have used the dataset having all age category people’s review, out of which we have filtered the data from the age group of 18 to 25.

In this paper, we have used NLTK for frequency counter, aspect-based sentiment analysis, word cloud and various Machine learning algorithms like Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm, Multinomial Naïve Bayes algorithm and RandomForestClassifier and the hybrid of these four ML algorithms.

A. NLTK for frequency counter:

NLTK is the platform for building Python programs working with natural language. It provides interfaces to over 50 corpora and lexical resources as well as a suite of text processing libraries for classification, parsing, semantic reasoning. The FreqDist() function of NLTK (nltk.org, 2023) to count the frequency of features. A frequency distribution records the number of times each outcome of an experiment has occurred.

B. Sentiment Analysis and its Types:

Sentiment Analysis is one of the most popular applications of Natural Language Processing. It is the process of identifying and categorizing opinions expressed in any text to determine whether the writer's attitude towards a particular topic, product, hotel, movie etc. is positive, negative, or neutral. The data for performing sentiment analysis can be taken from various resources like face book, twitter, article and hence it can be in different format like xml file, JSON file, csv file or simple text file. (K. Beena, 2021).

The analysis of the sentiment, or in general of the opinion, can be performed at any of the four different levels of detail, from the most generic to the most specific, such as document-level, sentence-level, aspect-level, and concept-level. (Hemmatian F.,2019) The document-level analysis (Pontiki M.,2016) is used to understand the polarity of a whole document product (Behdenna S.,2018), news article (ShirsatVS.,2017), a post, a tweet (Gurini D.,2013) reviews are few examples of document level sentiment analysis. Here, the information is quite general, as it finds the polarity of many sentences as a unique positive or negative. Lexicon-based approaches for document-level analysis typically identify the polarity of each term and then aggregate their polarity scores to classify the sentiment of the whole document.

Considering the level of importance of each word in this kind of approach could improve the accuracy of the classification. sentence-level SA (Appel O.,2016).

The aim is to understand if a sentence has a positive or negative polarity. Usually, a sentence level approach can be used also to analyze the sentiment of a complete document by analyzing its sentences and using an aggregation operator to combine the polarity of each sentence to obtain the global polarity of the document (Fang X, 2015). An analysis at the documents or sentence-level provides useful insights regarding the opinion of users about specific entities, but they do not allow to understand which elements, features, or aspects of such entities have influenced the (positive or negative) opinion. To perform such a kind of analysis, aspect-level sentiment analysis should be performed (Hu M, Liu B, 2004).

This level of analysis clearly provides a more accurate result if compared with document and sentence-level analysis. The idea of concept level sentiment analysis is to have machines able to deeply understand the natural language and in particular, to understand emotions, opinions, sentiments. Such kind of approaches are based on semantic analysis techniques able to identify and analyze the concepts in a text.

C. TextBlob Sentiment Analysis:

It is a simple python library -API used especially for sentiment analysis. Textblob sentiment analyzer returns the two properties for a particular given sentence: one of them is the Polarity, which is a float value between [-1,1], where -1 indicates negative sentiment and +1 indicates positive sentiments. Though VADER gives better outcome compared to TextBlob for KNN.(F. Fazrin,2022)

D. Spacy Sentiment Analysis:

spacytextblob is a pipeline component that enables sentiment analysis using the TextBlob (A. K. Singh, 2021)

E. VADER Sentiment Analysis

VADER is abbreviation for “Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner” and is available under the MIT License. The VADER tool was released in 2014. It uses a lexicon driven approach and additional heuristics for rating the input. It offers consistent ratings and requires no training data, as VADER is not a machine learning approach. It achieved remarkable scores for multiple domains such as tweets, movie or product reviews. (Hutto, C.J.,2014).

VADER is a rule-based sentiment analysis tool to express the sentiments on a given text. ([Yang, S. E. (n.d.),2019] It is used to label the dataset into positive or negative sentiment score, based on whether its value exceeds 0.5 or not.

The compound score can be calculated as the sum of all lexicon ratings which are normalized ones. (NIPS-2019) VADER works better than TextBlob for the text, taken from either social media or any web sources. (V. Bonta, 2019)

F. Word Cloud:

The Goole Cloud Natural Language API (n.d.,2023) Retrieved from Natural Language AI: <https://cloud.google.com/natural-language> uses machine learning techniques to support different tasks of natural language analysis, among which entity recognition, content classification, and sentiment analysis. In particular, the library supports both sentiment analysis and aspect-based sentiment analysis, at a document or sentence level. The polarity of the sentiment is given in the range [-1; +1].

G. Support Vector Machine Algorithm:

Support Vectors are simply the coordinates of individual observation. The SVM classifier is a frontier which best segregates the two classes (hyper-plane/ line). In SVM, it is required to select the hyper-plane which segregates the two classes better. If we can't find linear hyperplane between the two classes, then it is required to introduce additional feature. (S. Vanaja,, 2018)

H. Multinomial Naïve Bayes Algorithm:

Multinomial Naïve Bayes classifier works on the concept of term frequency (TF). TF means the number of times the word occurs in a document. Multinomial Naïve Bayes is used to find two facts that whether the word exists in a document or not as well as that words frequency in that document. (Tyagi, A., 2019).

I. Random Forest Algorithm:

Random Forest algorithm is a supervised machine learning algorithm used for classification. It works based on the concept of ensemble learning, in which number of decision trees get various subsets of the data set. Here, all decision trees predict the output for the new data and the final class of that new data is considered as most of the outcome predicted from all decision trees. (Sarraf, T., 2020)

J. K Nearest Neighbor Algorithm:

The K Nearest Neighbor algorithm takes all the given data and classifies a new data point based on the similarity. This means when new data appears then it can be easily classified into a category which is most suitable. That is, this algorithm at the training phase just stores the dataset and when it gets new data, then it classifies that data into a category that is much like the new data.

This algorithm first selects the number K of the neighbors (to get the exact k-value we need to test the model for each expected k-value.). Then, it calculates the minkowski distance of K number of neighbors. After that, it takes the k Nearest Neighbors as per the calculated minkowski distance. Among the identified k neighbors, it counts the number of the data points in each category. It then assigns the new data points to that category for which the number of the neighbor is maximum. (Pramesti, D., 2020)

III METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed incorporates a multifaceted approach to analyze sentiments towards non-Indian brands within the framework of the Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan. Firstly, the Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK) is utilized for preprocessing and tokenization of textual data. Subsequently, Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) is employed to extract specific aspects of the brands under scrutiny and gauge sentiment towards each aspect separately. Supervised Learning techniques, including Support Vector Machines (SVM), Multinomial Naive Bayes (MNB), Random Forest Classifier (RFC), and K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) algorithms, are then applied to model sentiment polarity based on the extracted features. Additionally, a Hybrid Ensemble Learning approach is adopted to integrate the outputs of multiple classifiers for improved accuracy and robustness in sentiment prediction. This comprehensive methodology ensures a thorough exploration of the opinions held by the younger generation regarding non-Indian brands amidst the backdrop of India's self-reliance campaign.

K. Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model:

Figure 1: Hybrid Ensemble classification Model.

For developing Hybrid Ensemble classification Model, we defined each of the four machine learning models – SVM, MNB, RFC and KNN - 5 times that results in a combination of a total of 20 weak learners as shown in figure 1. Finally, we used Max Voting Classifier method where the class which has been predicted mostly by the weak learners will be the final class prediction of the ensemble model. (Dr. Vaibhav Kumar, 2021).

IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A typical model of NLTK and Supervised Learning Approach to Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis of Global Brands:

Figure 2 shows A typical model of NLTK and Supervised Learning Approach to Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis of Global Brands.

Figure 2: Typical Aspect Based Sentiment Analysis and NLTK and supervised learning model.

A. Collection of data:

We have used Kaggle dataset 'Womens Clothing E-Commerce Reviews.csv' file for our study, which has 23486 rows.

The URL for this file is <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/nicapotato/womens-ecommerce-clothing-reviews> which has a total of 23486 rows of data. One of the columns of this dataset is age. Here this paper finds the younger generation selection criteria for buying the product. So, the data has been filtered for the age group of 18 to 25. After filtering, the total data comes out to be 1223. So, this study has been made on 1223 data of the total data set of 23486 rows.

B. Preprocessing data:

We have applied all data preprocessing techniques like,

C. Performing Aspect Extraction & sentiment analysis on Kaggle dataset:

We first fetched the data and pre-processed the data. Next, we converted each input sentence into tokens. If a word has some specific meaning, that is if it is a semantic argument-nsubj, and if it is a noun then it is considered as the aspect name. If any next token in the sentence is empty or some adverb and adjective or simply adjective, then it is considered as aspect extraction. E.g. for the sentence – The Product is very attractive. Aspect: Product and Description: very attractive. Next. We found its sentiment value using Vader Sentiment Analysis. And consider only those features, whose sentiment value is greater than +0.5 for the popular feature.

We performed aspect-based analysis on Kaggle data using to find the attributes and their description from 'reviewText' column of 'Womens Clothing E-Commerce Reviews.csv' file. it looks like below:

Aspect and its Description Extraction

```
[{'aspect': 'color', 'description': 'great'}, {'aspect': 'shirt', 'description': 'perfect'},
```

We have taken just the description into consideration. As shown in the example ‘perfect’ can be one of the features that tempts user to buy that product. We have found sentiment score of each description as shown above. As it is too difficult to take every description into consideration, we have just shown the first 10 descriptions along with its sentiment score, whose sentiment is > 0.5.

Below is shown the features of non-Indian Brands, which, along with its textblob, spacy and the VADER sentiment score.

```
ASPECT, ASPECT EXTRACTION AND ITS TextBlob, Spacy and VADER SCORE  
[{'aspect': 'color', 'description': 'great'}, {'aspect': 'shirt', 'description': 'perfect'},  
['great', 'perfect', 'great', 'perfect', 'great', 'perfect', 'great', 'great', 'perfect', 'pe  
[0.6249, 0.5719, 0.6249, 0.5719, 0.6249, 0.5719, 0.6249, 0.6249, 0.5719, 0.5719, 0.5719, 0.62  
[0.5, 0.5, 0.8, 0.5, 1.0, 0.8, 0.5, 0.5, 1.0, 0.6, 0.5, 0.8, 0.5, 1.0, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.  
[0.5, 0.5, 0.8, 0.5, 1.0, 0.8, 0.5, 0.5, 1.0, 0.6, 0.5, 0.8, 0.5, 1.0, 0.6, 0.5, 0.5, 0.5, 0.
```

D. Applying TextBlob, Spacy and VADER Sentiment Analysis:

There are three separate APIs available in Python as Textblob, SpacyTextBlob and VADER sentiment analysis to find the words polarity which gives values from +1.0 to -1.0. The five

categories of sentiment considered in this paper. Being 5 as most positive, whose values considered as 0.5 to 1 polarity, 4 is positive, whose values considered as greater than zero and less than 0.5, 3 to be the neutral, considered as zero polarity, 2 as the negative sentiment with polarity between zero (exclusive) polarity and -.5 (exclusive) polarity and 1 considered as most negative sentiment with polarity between -0.5 to -1.0, both inclusive. On the basis of VADER sentiment analysis, the frequency distribution of features has been calculated and wordCloud is designed. . To draw the frequency distribution graph of features against the count, the first 15 features we have considered.

E: Applying Supervised Learning Algorithms and Hybrid Model:

After finding the frequency distribution and wordCloud, the X is considered as the aspect-feature and y is considered the sentiment analysis score (5 to 1) as per the textblob API and the ML algorithms applied to the split of training and test data with the ratio 70:30. There are four ML algorithms we studied and also the hybrid model we applied. In the similar fashion, we studied the Spacytextblob and the VADAR sentiment analysis algorithm.

TextBlob and supervised Learning Algorithms:

As shown in figure 3, for the SVM- TextBlob, total 25, 271, 648, 359, and 368 are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 15, 1, 2, 19 and 6 data misclassified. As per MNC - TextBlob, 25, 269, 647, 359 and 367 are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 18,1,1,19,1,6, and 1 data misclassified. As per RFC - TextBlob, total 25,272, 648, 360 and 363 are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 15,1,18,1,7 and 4 data misclassified. As per KNN - TextBlob, total 25,269,647,347, and 363 data are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 17,1,1,2,28,3 and 10 data misclassified.

Figure 3: SVM and MNB –TextBlob

Figure 4: RFC and KNN – TextBlob

Figure 5: Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model – TextBlob

As per Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model - TextBlob, total 25, 272, 647, 360 and 365 data are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 15, 1, 1, 18, 1, 8, and 1 data misclassified, which is lowest of all.

Spacy and supervised Learning Algorithms:

As per SVM -Spacy, As shown in figure 3, for the SVM- TextBlob, total 25, 271, 648, 359, and 368 are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 15, 1, 2, 19 and 6 data misclassified. As per MNC - TextBlob, 25, 269, 647, 359 and 367 are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 18, 1, 1, 19, 1, 6, and 1 data misclassified. As per RFC - TextBlob, total 25, 272, 648, 360 and 363 are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 15, 1, 18, 1, 7 and 4 data misclassified. As per KNN - TextBlob, total 25, 269, 647, 347, and 363 data are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 17, 1, 1, 2, 28, 3 and 10 data misclassified.

Figure 6: SVM and MNB – SpacyTextBlob

Figure 7: RFC and KNN – SpacyTextBlob

As per Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model - TextBlob, total 25,272, 647, 360 and 365 data are classified correctly with sentiment 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively, whereas 15,1,1,18,1,8, and 1 data misclassified, which is lowest of all.

Figure 8: Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model – SpacyTextBlob

VADER and supervised Learning Algorithms:

As per SVM -VADER, 1882 data classified correctly whereas 32 data misclassified. As per MNB -VADER, 1677 data classified correctly whereas 37 data misclassified. As per RFC -VADER, 1682 data classified correctly whereas 32 data misclassified. As per KNN -VADER, 1669 data classified correctly whereas 45 data misclassified. As per Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model -VADER, 1682 data classified correctly whereas only 32 data misclassified.

Figure 9: SVM – VADER and MNB – VADER

Figure 10: RFC and KNN – VADER

Figure 11: Hybrid Ensemble Learning Model – VADER

F: NLTK Frequency Counter

In NLTK, the nltk package has one function `FreqDist()`, which one parameter as list corpus, which accepts list and finds frequency of each unique word. The output from frequency counter what we received is as shown in figure 12.

Figure 12: Line chart and WordCloud

Figure 12 shows that the color / after wash/ variety / size / jeans is great, the product / shirt /skirt /print / size / dress / waist is perfect, pant / romper suit / opaque look / look / print is super, thought / softness / shirt / Gap / sandal / shirt / Jeans is best, portion (lot) / pant / shirt / skirt is super cute. It further shows that the most positive features of what the respondents found as per the dataset of Kaggle in global brand cloths are great, perfect, super, best, vibrant, rich, super cute, free, well fit, kind, fun, happier, cuter and cutest. The frequency of each of the features are as: {'great': 276, 'perfect': 213, 'super': 24, 'best': 19, 'super cute': 9,

'rich': 7, 'vibrant': 7, 'also great': 5, 'strong': 4, 'super soft': 3, 'free': 2, 'fun': 2, 'ideal': 2, 'much cuter': 2, 'quality great': 2, 'well cute': 2}

V. CONCLUSION

The line chart has been plotted with plot() function of Python. The WordCloud() function imported from wordcloud package. The line chart shows the most popular features people liked in global brands in decreasing order. WordCloud is a visualization technique for text data. In the WordCloud each word is picturized with its importance in the context or its frequency.

Algorithm/accuracy	TextBlob	SpacyTextBlob	VADER
SVC	0.9695	0.9695	0.9832
Multinomial Naïve Bayes	0.9657	0.9657	0.9765
Random Forest	0.9682	0.9682	0.9830
KNN	0.9552	0.9552	0.9735
Hybrid Ensemble Model	0.9690	0.9690	0.9820

Table 1: Comparative data of TextBlob, SpacyTextBlob and VADAR sentiment analysis

As per table 1, the conclusion can be drawn that TextBlob and SpacyTextBlob yield the same results. The VADAR sentiment analysis has shown more accuracy than the other two APIs. So further work can be done only using VADER sentiment analysis. There is not much improvement in using Hybrid Ensemble learning model because we have classified the aspects and not the direct reviews. Because we classified the aspects and on the aspects, we applied the ML algorithms, It has given wonderful accuracy in the base work itself. Very little fine tuning could be done with the hybrid ensemble learning model. But even though the scope of improvement was not there, the hybrid ensemble learning model has shown minor improvement in all categories of sentiment analysis.

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